

Tree Species Diversity and Composition of Sailam, Mizoram, North-East India

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This study focused on assessing the diversity and community structure of Sailam forest area. The Shannon-Weiner index was calculated to be 4.02, which is higher than the majority of studies conducted in other tropical forests. These findings indicate a high tree diversity and community stability at the study site. The overall Simpson's index value was determined to be 0.96. This value is comparable to other forest areas, such as Hmuifang in Mizoram (Sharma *et al.*, 2018) and deciduous forests of Andhra Pradesh (Naidu *et al.*, 2018), and higher than most tropical forests in India. The Simpson's index values for different Indian tropical forests typically range from 0.03 to 0.92, with an average value of 0.06. The present study's recorded value is consistent with previous estimates. Additionally, the study observed a decrease in species richness and density with increasing tree size classes within the plot area. The species with the highest abundance in the plot was *Schima wallichii*, with an estimated value of 4.45 individuals per plot. These findings contribute to our understanding of the diversity and community structure of the studied forest area.

Keywords: Tree diversity, Shannon-Weiner Diversity Index, Simpson's Dominance Index, Mizoram.